

The Emperor's Insects: Revisiting the Mantodea of Jules-César Savigny from Napoleon's Campaign in Egypt and Ottoman Syria

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Abstract. The Mantodea figures published in the *Description de l'Égypte* under Jules-César Savigny are reviewed, emphasizing their artistic execution and subsequent taxonomic interpretation. Each engraving depicting mantises is analyzed for their assigned correspondence to known species by historical authors.

Jules-César Savigny (1777–1851) was one of the naturalists formally attached to Napoleon Bonaparte's Egyptian expedition, a campaign that combined military objectives with an unprecedented scientific enterprise. Savigny's role within this corps of savants was that of zoological collector, anatomist, and morphological authority. Although best known broadly for his contributions to arthropod anatomy, his work on Mantodea that was executed during and immediately following the expedition represents one of the most significant early visual records of the order.

Savigny accompanied the French army throughout its movements in Egypt and later into Ottoman Syria (the region now corresponding to modern-day Israel, not the modern country of Syria) between 1798 and 1801. His collecting activity followed the logistical routes of the campaign, with material gathered from principal Egyptian localities occupied by the army, including Alexandria, Rosetta, Damietta, Cairo, and Suez, as well as from Ottoman Syrian stations such as El-Arish, Gaza, Jaffa, and Acre. The scientific expedition was inseparable from the military one, and no independent zoological itinerary existed outside the army's advance and retreat.

Following the French withdrawal from Egypt in 1801, Savigny returned to France with his collections, drawings, and preparatory materials. Almost immediately thereafter, he began the scientific treatment of this material, overseeing the preparation of a series of engraved plates for the monumental *Description de l'Égypte*. These engravings depict entire specimen habitues alongside enlarged anatomical details: head capsules, mouthparts, antennae, legs, and wings were all rendered with exceptional precision. Savigny exercised strict anatomical and terminological control over these figures, the original drawings for which were executed under his direct supervision by professional natural history artists. Savigny credited Meynier, Nicolas Huet, and most prominently, Jean-Gabriel Prêtre as responsible for the drawings, a point later emphasized by Krauss (1890: 227) in his detailed historical review. Jean-Gabriel Prêtre (1768–1849), a Swiss-born French painter and draughtsman, was one of the leading natural history illustrators of the early 19th century; attached to the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle in Paris and earlier to Empress Joséphine's menagerie at Malmaison, he produced a vast number of precise

watercolors and drawings of animals (including many invertebrates) that formed the basis for engraved plates in major works, including Savigny's sections of the *Description de l'Égypte*. Nicolas Huet (the Younger, 1770–1830), from a prominent family of French animal artists, was also a skilled natural history illustrator who participated in the Egyptian expedition and contributed drawings to various zoological plates in the *Description de l'Égypte*. Meynier (likely Jean-Baptiste Meunier, sometimes rendered variably in records) is less extensively documented but was similarly credited alongside Prêtre and Huet for certain invertebrate drawings under Savigny's direction.

Tragically, Savigny's scientific productivity was curtailed by progressive and ultimately complete blindness, accompanied by severe and chronic pain. Although he succeeded in completing the engraved plates, he was no longer able to prepare the accompanying descriptive text or formally treat the zoological material taxonomically. As a result, none of the Mantodea depicted by Savigny were described or named by him, and no binomials were proposed in connection with his mantis figures. This circumstance proved decisive for the later taxonomic fate of the material. Crucially, Savigny retained personal possession of his original specimens, drawings, manuscripts, and all associated collection records throughout his life, refusing to deposit them in any public institution or entrust them to another researcher—even after French government intervention in 1825. In particular, he neither published nor handed over any detailed locality data or collection notes for the Mantodea he gathered during the expedition. Although this material is known to have been collected along the routes of the French campaign, the exact provenance of individual specimens remains unknown and could plausibly correspond to any locality occupied or traversed by Napoleon's army. The material is not known to survive today. Consequently, the engraved plates published in the Panckoucke edition of *Description de l'Égypte* represent the sole extant primary evidence for Savigny's Mantodea and the lack of original descriptions meant that formal nomenclatural treatment was deferred to subsequent authors.

In 1826, Victor Audouin, a former student of Savigny, was tasked with producing an explanatory text for Savigny's Mantodea plates. Lacking access to Savigny's original specimens or manuscripts, Audouin relied exclusively on Savigny's plates and adopted a deliberately conservative approach toward assigning any names to the species depicted therein. For the Mantodea, he introduced no new species names; he retained most illustrated forms within the broad genus *Mantis* Linné, 1758 but placed two distinctive figures under *Empusa* Illiger, 1798, consistent with the taxonomic understanding of the time. Following the 1826 publication of the plates, a series of authors retroactively assigned binomials by interpreting Savigny's figures in conjunction with later material. But as with Audouin, at no point during this period were Savigny's original mantis specimens examined directly; all taxonomic decisions rested exclusively on the engraved plates. Further, in the absence of locality data or collection notes for the depicted species, the precise geographic origins of the illustrated mantises could not be determined by these later workers. As a result, the provenance of the engraved specimens remained inferred rather than documented.

In 1890, Hermann Krauss published the first comprehensive synthesis of the scattered taxonomic treatments that had been applied to Savigny's illustrated Mantodea. His monograph summarized the subsequent names assigned to each depicted species and resolved several conflicting interpretations in the literature. Importantly, Krauss neither reproduced Savigny's original images nor claimed access to any specimens; rather, his principal contribution lay in collating and critically evaluating the post-Savignian nomenclatural history of these figures. This foundational effort was later extended by Storey in 1918, who undertook a systematic re-examination of all Orthoptera figured by Savigny in the *Description de l'Égypte*, with particular emphasis on reconciling Savigny's plates with the contemporary Egyptian fauna. Storey demonstrated that many figures long regarded as dubious, misidentified, or known only from Savigny's illustrations could, in fact, be confidently referred to well-established species, while also highlighting cases of erroneous geographic attribution and repeated renaming by later authors. The present study builds upon the successive syntheses of Krauss and Storey by incorporating the original Savigny engravings directly, allowing for direct reference and visual appreciation.

From a morphological and artistic standpoint, Savigny's Mantodea engravings stand apart from all comparable works of the period. Their anatomical fidelity, proportional accuracy, and clarity of detail are unmatched among early nineteenth-century treatments of Mantodea and far exceed those found in earlier illustrated compendia. Savigny's plates combine whole-body habitus figures with enlarged structural details in a manner that anticipates modern taxonomic illustration. Even where later authors disagreed on the identities of individual figures, the technical excellence of the engravings themselves has never been questioned. Under the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature, authorship of the Mantodea section of the *Description de l'Égypte* was attributed to Audouin (1826), not to Savigny, as Savigny never completed or published the descriptive text associated with the plates (ICZN, 1987).

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Tears come to my eyes when I contemplate these sublime plates, deprived both of text and of the author's explanation, delivered over to the plundering of interpreters who are rash or poorly informed; what entomologist does not lament the fate of a treasure of science so skillfully prepared and so dearly paid for! ~Dufour, 1888

Mantodea specimen male dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 8.1, aspect 1 ♂) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen male head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 8.1, aspects A~ & A) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen male antenna (Plate 1, Figure 8.1, aspect j) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 8.2, aspect 2 ♀) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female foreleg (Plate 1, Figure 8.2, aspect b) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 8.2, aspects A~ & A) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female mouthparts (Plate 1, Figure 8.2, aspects a, i, i~, o, u & u~) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female antenna (Plate 1, Figure 8.2, aspect j) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen nymph (Plate 1, Figure 8.3, aspect 3) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 8 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Empusa sp.*
 Burmeister, 1838: 1012 *Empusa pauperata* (Fabricius, 1781)
 Audinet-Serville, 1838: 146 *Empusa pauperata* (Fabricius, 1781)
 Fischer von Waldheim, 1846: 95 *Empusa pauperata* (Fabricius, 1781)
 Cuvier, 1849: Plate 78 *Empusa pauperata* (Fabricius, 1781)
 Lucas, 1849: 9 *Empusa pauperata* (Fabricius, 1781)
 Saussure, 1870-71: 337 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841
 Brunner, 1882: 71 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841
 Westwood, 1889: 25 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841
 Krauss, 1890: 235 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841
 Werner, 1905: 55 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841
 Innes, 1912: 76 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841
 Storey, 1918: 57 *Empusa egena* Charpentier, 1841

Remarks. The species identity represented by Savigny's Plate I, Figure 8 series has long been obscured by the early misapplication of the composite name *pauperata*, an error that propagated through much of the nineteenth-century literature. As detailed by Anderson (2023: 48–49), *Mantis pauperata* Fabricius, 1781 was described from two syntypes originating from disparate regions: one specimen from Coromandel, India, and a second from Lusitania (Portugal/western Spain). Fabricius incorrectly regarded these two specimens as conspecific, thereby conflating an Indian taxon with a Mediterranean one. The Lusitanian specimen is now known to represent the widespread European species later described as *Mantis pennata* Thunberg, 1815, whereas the Coromandel specimen corresponds to the true Indian *pauperata*. In 1838, Burmeister was first to assign Savigny's Figure 8 series to *pauperata*, erroneously listing Thunberg's *pennata* as a synonym. Audinet-Serville followed suit, merely listing the figure as *Empusa pauperata* without commentary. These actions effectively entrenched Fabricius's original error in the literature for the next three decades.

Recognizing that Fabricius had united two non-conspecific taxa under *pauperata*, Charpentier (1841: 298) correctly restricted that name to the Indian species and acknowledged the Mediterranean population as distinct. To accommodate the latter, he introduced the name *egena*, explicitly associating it with material from southern Europe, North Africa, and adjacent regions. This represented a critical conceptual correction, even though this step was rendered unnecessary by the prior availability of *pennata*, which already occupied the name-bearing role for the Mediterranean taxon. Charpentier's failure to adopt *pennata* is notable, particularly since he explicitly cited Thunberg's work. This omission is plausibly explained by the fact that Thunberg did not specify a type locality or clearly delimit the geographic range of *pennata*, whereas Charpentier himself articulated a defined Mediterranean distribution for *egena*, leading him to regard the taxon as undescribed despite its prior availability.

Subsequent authors responded inconsistently to Charpentier's clarification. Fischer von Waldheim acknowledged Charpentier's distinction between *pauperata* and *egena* yet paradoxically continued to list Savigny's Figure 8 series under *pauperata*, whereas Cuvier and Lucas ignored Charpentier's work entirely, persisting in their attribution of Savigny's Figure 8 series to the composite name *pauperata*. A substantive shift occurred with Saussure, who was the first to apply *egena* to Savigny's Figure 8 series. Although this represented progress toward separating the taxa that Fabricius had confounded, Saussure nonetheless erred by using *egena* rather than the senior name *pennata*. Although incorrect, Saussure's use of *egena* proved influential. It was subsequently adopted by Brunner, Westwood, Krauss, Werner, Innes, and Storey, thereby establishing *egena* as the prevailing attribution of Savigny's Figure 8 series throughout the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. The nomenclatural issue was finally resolved by Giglio-Tos (1927: 639), who explicitly recognized *Empusa egenae* Charpentier, 1841 as a junior synonym of *Empusa pennata* (Thunberg, 1815). However, although this issue was addressed, the attribution of either name to Savigny's Figure 8 series was never reassessed.

The original classification error of Savigny's Figure 8 series rests upon Burmeister, who failed to address *Empusa fasciata* Brullé, 1832 in his 1838 treatment of *Empusa* Illiger, 1798. Notably, the absence of *fasciata* from Burmeister's work indicates that its omission, rather than any morphological incompatibility, underlies his misidentification of Savigny's Figure 8 series to *pauperata*. Brullé (1832: 85) himself explicitly addresses the confusion between *pauperata* and his new species in relation to Savigny's depicted species, noting that:

“[*fasciata*] resembles at first glance *Mantis pauperata* Fabr.; but it is readily distinguished by the banding of its anterior legs. It appears to have closer affinities with the species figured by Savigny (Egypt, Orthoptera, pl. I, fig. 8). The principle difference observed between these two insects lies in the spines on the sides of the pronotum—spines which constitute the character by which Savigny's species may be recognized.”

Additional morphological evidence reinforces this conclusion: in *pennata sensu pauperata* the metathoracic coxae are unlobed in both sexes, whereas the illustration of the female in Savigny's Figure 8 series distinctly shows salient lobes on the metathoracic coxae, a condition consistent with *fasciata* and incompatible with *pennata sensu pauperata*, in which such lobation is absent in both sexes.

Although Savigny provided no explicit locality data for his specimens, their provenance can be constrained by the documented route of Napoleon's Egyptian campaign, which proceeded from Egypt through what was then Ottoman Syria via the Mediterranean coast, largely within the bounds of modern Israel. As detailed by Simon et al. (2025: 279), *fasciata* is widespread in northern Israel and represents the most common *Empusa* species in that region. The geographic likelihood of Savigny's material originating from this corridor, combined with the diagnostic pronotal armature of the male, the metathoracic coxal lobation of the depicted female, and Brullé's contemporaneous and explicit association of Savigny's figures with *fasciata*, demonstrates that the Plate I, Figure 8 series represents *Empusa fasciata* Brullé,

1832. Accordingly, Savigny's figures constitute the earliest known depiction of *fasciata* and do not represent *pennata* under the misapplied name *pauperata*, nor under *egena*, which was later and unnecessarily introduced for *pennata*. The historical assignment of these figures to *pauperata* or its derivatives reflects successive interpretations of Fabricius's composite concept rather than the true species identity illustrated by Savigny.

Taxonomic Designation. *Empusa fasciata* Brullé, 1832

Mantodea specimen male dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 9.1, aspect 1 ♂) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen male antenna (Plate 1, Figure 9.1, aspect j) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female ventral habitus (Plate 1, Figure 9.2, aspect 2 ♀) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female foreleg (Plate 1, Figure 9.2, aspect b) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 9.2, aspect A & A~) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 9 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Empusa* sp.
Burmeister, 1838: 1012 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Audinet-Serville, 1838: 149 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Charpentier, 1844: 295 *Mantis mendica* Fabricius, 1775
Saussure, 1870-71: 329 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Westwood, 1889: 26 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Krauss, 1890: 236 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Werner, 1905: 56 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Innes, 1912: 77 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Storey, 1918: 57 *Blepharis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)
Ehrmann, 2002: 79 *Blepharopsis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)

Remarks. The species depicted by Savigny's Figure 9 series has exhibited a notably stable taxonomic interpretation over nearly two centuries. From the earliest post-Savigny treatments, the figure was consistently associated with the taxon originally described by Fabricius as *Mantis mendica*. Beginning with Burmeister and Audinet-Serville, the illustration was explicitly referred to *mendica*, reflecting Audinet-Serville's generic concept of *Blepharis* for this distinctive Saharo-Mediterranean lineage. Charpentier briefly reverted to Fabricius' original generic combination but this did not alter the prevailing species concept. Subsequent authors throughout the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, including Saussure, Westwood, Krauss, Werner, Innes, and Storey, all uniformly maintained the identification of Savigny's Figure 9 series with *mendica*. This continuity indicates that the diagnostic morphology illustrated by Savigny was consistently recognized as referable to the same well-defined species, with no substantive challenge to its identity. A nomenclatural adjustment became necessary when Rehn (1901: 316) recognized that *Blepharis* Audinet-Serville, 1831 was preoccupied by *Blepharis* Cuvier, 1817, rendering the mantodean generic name unavailable. This homonymy required the introduction of a replacement name, for which *Blepharopsis* was proposed. Ehrmann subsequently adopted this corrected generic placement, listing the species as *Blepharopsis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775), thereby bringing the nomenclature into compliance with the rules of zoological priority and homonymy.

Taxonomic Designation. *Blepharopsis mendica* (Fabricius, 1775)

Mantodea specimen male dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 10, aspect 1 ♂) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen male mouthparts (Plate 1, Figure 10, aspects a, i, o & u) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 10 between 1827-2002.

Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.

Burmeister, 1838: 1012 *Mantis* (*Stagmatoptera*) *bimaculata* Burmeister, 1838

Saussure, 1870-71: 219 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838) variation a

Brunner, 1882: 58 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)

Westwood, 1889: 14 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)

Krauss, 1890: 236 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)

Werner, 1905: 52 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)

Innes, 1912: 65 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)

Innes, 1912: 66 *Mantis religiosa* Linné, 1758

Storey, 1918: 50 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)

La Greca, 1967: 499 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)

Ehrmann, 2002: 325 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)

Mantodea specimen female dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 11, aspect 1 ♀) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female foreleg (Plate 1, Figure 11, aspect b) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 11, aspect A) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 11 between 1827-2002.

Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.

Burmeister, 1838: 1012 *Mantis* (*Stagmatoptera*) *bimaculata* Burmeister, 1838

Lucas, 1849: 10 *Mantis bimaculata* Burmeister, 1838

Saussure, 1870-71: 219 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838) variation a
Brunner, 1882: 58 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Westwood, 1889: 14 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Krauss, 1890: 236 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Werner, 1905: 52 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Innes, 1912: 65 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Innes, 1912: 66 *Mantis religiosa* Linné, 1758
Storey, 1918: 50 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
La Greca, 1967: 499 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)
Ehrmann, 2002: 325 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)

Remarks. Burmeister (1838: 537) described *bimaculata* as an ash-gray to brownish species with serrated pronotal margins and forewings sprinkled with white spots and bearing a conspicuous stigma. He reported a broad distribution for the species, spanning Egypt, Nubia (modern-day Sudan and southern Egypt), and Abyssinia (modern-day Ethiopia and Eritrea). Importantly, Burmeister explicitly assigned Savigny's Figures 10–11 to *bimaculata*, which demonstrates that he considered the illustrated male–female pair to be conspecific with his female holotype and deliberately linked his name-bearing concept to Savigny's illustrated figures. The synonymy of *bimaculata* with *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775) was first formally established by Giglio-Tos (1912: 144), as the latter was described from Alexandria several decades earlier; the synonymy remains presently accepted in current taxonomy. Although the type material of *viridis* was already lost at the time of Burmeister's writing, Forskål's description was clearly based on a green-phased individual, as reflected in the epithet *viridis* itself. Faced with a brown-phased specimen from the same general region, Burmeister evidently concluded that his material represented a species distinct from Forskål's *viridis*, rather than a chromatic variant within a single, highly variable taxon. No specimens bearing the name *bimaculata* are currently known in the Berlin collections (ZMB) nor in the Hamburg or Munich holdings that contain *Sphodromantis* or *Hierodula* material. Furthermore, Burmeister's other types are deposited at the indicated institutions and are not known to have been deposited anywhere else. This situation forces the conclusion that the *bimaculata* holotype must also be regarded as lost. Nevertheless, Burmeister's explicit association of *bimaculata* with Savigny's figures, and thereby *viridis* by synonymy, supplies a stable and informative iconotype proxy for his species concept even in the absence of both the *viridis* and *bimaculata* holotypes.

Savigny's Figures 10–11 have erroneously been treated as varieties of the distinct species depicted in Figure 13 for well over a century. However, the male depicted in Figure 10 and the male depicted in Figure 13 express a coordinated suite of differences in forewing architecture, stigma morphology, head–pronotum proportionality, and overall size, which when taken together are more consistent with species-level separation than with simple intraspecific variation. Most salient is the configuration of the forewing costal area: in Figure 10, the base of the costal area is angularly expanded, producing a more abruptly widening, shouldered appearance at the costal base; in Figure 13, that same region is confluent at the base, suggesting a more gradual integration of the costal field. Concordant with this, the stigma differs sharply: in Figure 10 it is more prominent, larger, oval, and surrounded by obvious darkened maculation; in Figure 13 it is smaller, more angular, and exhibits a markedly reduced dark outline. Proportional morphology further supports separation: in Figure 10 the head capsule width is approximately comparable to the supracoxal dilation of the pronotum, producing a balanced head to dilation ratio; in Figure 13 the head capsule is conspicuously wider relative to the supracoxal dilation, giving the impression of a narrower pronotal platform beneath a broader head. Finally, the overall habitus and all corresponding dimensions of Figure 13 are plainly smaller than those of Figure 10. On this basis, Figures 10–11 are here definitively attributed to *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775), and *Mantis* (*Stagmatoptera*) *bimaculata* Burmeister, 1838 is upheld as a junior synonym of *viridis*, while *bioculata*, which is depicted in Figure 13, is excluded from this species concept.

Taxonomic Designation. *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)

Mantodea specimen nymph (Plate 1, Figure 12, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 12 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
 Saussure, 1870-71: 219 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838) nymph
 Brunner, 1882: 58 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
 Westwood, 1889: 14 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
 Krauss, 1890: 236 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
 Werner, 1905: 52 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
 Innes, 1912: 65 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
 Innes, 1912: 66 *Mantis religiosa* Linné, 1758
 Storey, 1918: 50 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
 La Greca, 1967: 499 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)
 Ehrmann, 2002: 325 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)

Remarks. Figure 12 presents a clear lateral aspect of the specimen that exposes the anterior surface of the foreleg. This perspective is taxonomically informative, as the anterior surface of the forecoxae in *Mantis* Linné, 1758 typically bear a basal spot in combination with a series of callous tubercles along with the tibial spur groove being well developed and distinctly marked. By contrast, in *Sphodromantis* Stål, 1871 the interior surface of the forecoxae is characteristically maculated with three to four round, callous spots. These latter features are not evident in Savigny's Figure 12, whose foreleg morphology instead accords with *Mantis*. Importantly, Burmeister made no reference to Savigny's Figure 12 when establishing *bimaculata* or *bioculata*, indicating that the nymph did not inform his species concepts. It was Saussure who first referred the nymph of Figure 12 to *bioculata*, doing so in the context of his synthesis that united *bimaculata* and *bioculata* as varieties of a single species. This attribution was subsequently repeated without reassessment by later authors, apparently because the engraving itself was seldom examined in detail. Innes was the only author to question this placement, suggesting that the nymph might instead be referable to *religiosa*. However, Innes inadvertently listed Savigny's entire figure series (10–13) twice—once under *bioculata* and again under *religiosa*—a clerical error that obscured his intent. It is far more likely that Innes meant to isolate Figure 12 alone as *religiosa*, not the entire series. This nuance was

overlooked by Storey, who dismissed Innes' suggestion as a "slip" and rejected it wholesale, rather than recognizing that the error lay in scope rather than in identification. On morphological grounds, the correct interpretation is that Figure 12 represents a nymph of *religiosa*. The overall habitus, foreleg maculation, and absence of *Sphodromantis*-type coxal spotting are fully consistent with *religiosa*, a species that, although less common, is well documented from the region in which Napoleon's army marched through and temporarily occupied.

Taxonomic Designation. *Mantis religiosa* Linné, 1758

Mantodea specimen male dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 13, aspect 1 ♂) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 13 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
Burmeister, 1838: 1012 *Mantis* (*Stagmatoptera*) *bioculata* Burmeister, 1838
Saussure, 1870-71: 219 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838) variation b
Brunner, 1882: 58 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Westwood, 1889: 14 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Krauss, 1890: 236-237 *Hierodula bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Werner, 1905: 52 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Innes, 1912: 65 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
Innes, 1912: 66 *Mantis religiosa* Linné, 1758
Storey, 1918: 50 *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838)
La Greca, 1967: 499 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)
Ehrmann, 2002: 325 *Sphodromantis viridis* (Forskål, 1775)

Remarks. Burmeister (1838: 537) described *bioculata* as a bright green species with the anteroventral margin of the forecoxae bearing numerous spines and the forewings marked by a distinct oval white stigma bordered with dark brown. He explicitly differentiated the sexes, noting a more slender habitus and a narrower, finely granulated pronotum in the male, and a broader, more strongly serrated pronotum in the female. The stated distribution of this species encompassed Egypt, Nubia, and Syria. Burmeister directly attributed Savigny's Figure 13 to the male of his *bioculata* but it is clear that his species concept was not derived solely from Savigny's illustrations. His diagnosis includes chromatic characters and a bilateral sexual comparison that Savigny's plates cannot provide, as Savigny illustrated only a single male without color. Burmeister's *bioculata* must therefore have been based on at least one male–female pair personally examined by him, with Savigny's Figure 13 treated as conspecific by visual correspondence. As with *bimaculata*, no specimens labeled as *bioculata* are currently known from the Berlin collections (ZMB), where Burmeister's types are otherwise known to have been deposited, nor from the Hamburg or Munich holdings of *Sphodromantis* or *Hierodula*. The syntypes of *bioculata* must therefore be regarded as lost, and Savigny's Figure 13 consequently serves as the only extant original representation of the species concept (an iconotype in the historical sense, not a name-bearing type under the ICZN).

Saussure (1869: 67) initially maintained *bimaculata* and *bioculata* as distinct based primarily on pronotal shape, a comparatively plastic character when considered in isolation, despite the presence of additional diagnostic characters separating these geographically disparate species that were discussed earlier. The following year, while working exclusively with North African material, Saussure erroneously treated these distinct species as mere varieties of a single species under the name *bioculata*. This decision was reached in the absence of accessible type specimens for either species, which were likely already unavailable to Saussure at that time. As a substitute for these missing holotypes, had Saussure examined Savigny's illustrations that were respectively linked to both species by Burmeister, it would have been evident that two distinct species are depicted. Instead, Saussure expanded the scope of the name *bioculata* to encompass two biologically distinct populations, thereby conflating separate species under a single epithet. This action had lasting consequences, for once *bimaculata* was later shown to be a junior synonym of *viridis*, Saussure's expanded concept of *bioculata* was automatically drawn into synonymy with *viridis* as well.

Further confusing this taxonomy, Saussure (1870–1871: 230) unknowingly introduced a synonym to represent a species that was already described under *bioculata* by Burmeister and depicted in Figure 13 by Savigny. *Hierodula trimacula* was described from a single female specimen that Saussure reported as originating from “Sina”. Roy (2010: 361) examined the *trimacula* holotype and documented that it bears the label “Perse Aucher 16–40” in the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN), collected by Pierre Martin Rémi Aucher-Éloy during his Middle Eastern expeditions of the 1830s. The term “Perse” in nineteenth-century labeling practice was frequently employed as a broad geographic designation for

portions of the Near East and western Asia. Recent work by Mirzaee et al. (2026: 12) has definitively demonstrated that *trimacula* does not occur in Iran. Simultaneous work by Simon et al. (2025) confirms that no verified museum or field records support the presence of *trimacula* in Israel. This effectively excludes modern Iran as the provenance of the *trimacula* holotype and, in conjunction with Simon et al.'s comprehensive treatment of Israeli Mantodea, renders a Levantine origin unsupported by available faunal evidence. Saussure's specification of "Sina" should therefore be understood as an interpretive narrowing of the broader and imprecise regional label "Perse," most plausibly referring to the Sinai Peninsula rather than representing an independently verified locality.

Saussure's original description and illustration of *trimacula* correspond closely with Burmeister's description of *bioculata* and with Savigny's Figure 13. Given that the Sinai Peninsula emerges as the most parsimonious historical interpretation of the provenance of *trimacula*, this location accords with Burmeister's stated distribution of *bioculata* as encompassing Egypt and [Ottoman era] Syria as well as the historical context of Napoleon's occupation and Savigny's collection efforts in the region. Thus, properly resolved, Saussure should have synonymized *bimaculata* with *viridis*, retained *bioculata* as a distinct species, and had no cause to describe *trimacula* at all. Instead, he mistakenly subsumed a valid species into a conglomerate concept and erected an unnecessary new name for a taxon already described—thereby introducing a century of avoidable taxonomic confusion.

Mantis (Stagmatoptera) bioculata Burmeister, 1838 and *Hierodula trimacula* Saussure, 1870 are herein treated as subjective synonyms based on concordant morphology and historical evidence. Although *trimacula* has been widely used as a valid name in modern literature, *bioculata* is the senior available name and was used as a valid species-group name after 1899 (Werner 1905; Innes 1912; Storey 1918). Consequently, the conditions required for automatic reversal of precedence under ICZN Article 23.9.1 are not met, as the senior synonym *bioculata* was used as a valid name after 1899 and the requirements of prevailing usage for *trimacula* cannot override priority under the present circumstances. In accordance with the Principle of Priority (ICZN Article 23.1), *bioculata* is therefore reinstated as the valid name, with *trimacula* treated as a junior subjective synonym. The species is correctly placed in *Sphodromantis*, following the generic transfer by Kaltenbach (1982: 42). Accordingly, the valid and correct combination is *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838), with *Hierodula trimacula* Saussure, 1870 placed in synonymy.

Taxonomic Designation. *Sphodromantis bioculata* (Burmeister, 1838) **stat. rev.** = *Hierodula trimacula* Saussure, 1870 **syn. nov.**

Mantodea specimen dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 14, aspect 1 ♀) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 14, aspect A~) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 14 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
- Saussure, 1870-71: 256 *Iris (Fischeria) baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Brunner, 1882: 64 *Fischeria baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Westwood, 1889: 9 *Fischeria baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Krauss, 1890: 237 *Fischeria baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Werner, 1905: 55 *Fischeria baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Innes, 1912: 69 *Fischeria baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Storey, 1918: 57 *Fischeria baetica* (Rambur, 1838)
- Giglio-Tos, 1927: 484 *Eufischeriella fasciata* (Thunberg, 1815)
- Ehrmann, 2002: 310 *Rivetina baetica* (Rambur, 1838)

Remarks. Savigny designated Figure 14 with the female (♀) symbol; however, the morphological evidence depicted in the engraving clearly indicates that the specimen represents a male. The depicted specimen is macropterous with a slender abdomen that terminates in well-defined male genital structures, leaving little ambiguity as to its sex. Saussure (1870–1871: 256), evidently influenced by the contradictory female symbol accompanying the figure, speculated that “the figured insect was composed using the body and wings of a male, to which the abdomen of a female had been added,” thereby suggesting an artificial composite reconstruction. This interpretation is not supported by the morphology shown in the plate. Krauss (1890: 237) correctly rejected Saussure’s conjecture, noting that “the designation ♀ is incorrect; the figure represents a ♂; what prompted Saussure to make the remark is unclear, since the figure shows a completely natural, male abdomen with the characteristic terminal organs”.

The taxonomic treatment of Savigny’s Figure 14 has been consistent in species-level attribution, though complicated by issues of homonymy and nomenclatural oversight. Thunberg (1815: 292–293) described *Mantis fasciata* from a female specimen originating from Morocco, the holotype of which remains extant in the Thunberg collection at the Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University. However, *Mantis fasciata* Thunberg, 1815 is a junior homonym of *Mantis fasciata* Manuel, 1797 and was therefore unavailable from the time of its publication. Giglio-Tos (1916: 21) synonymized Thunberg’s *fasciata* with *Mantis baetica* Rambur, 1838 and accorded priority to *fasciata* as the senior synonym, subsequently maintaining this treatment in 1927 under the combination *Eufischeriella fasciata*. In doing so, Giglio-Tos failed to recognize the homonymy rendering Thunberg’s name permanently unavailable under the Code, and thus ineligible for use as either a valid name or a senior synonym. As a result, the application of *fasciata*

during this period represents a nomenclatural error rather than a legitimate exercise of priority. Anderson (2024: 28) clarified this issue by recognizing *baetica* as the appropriate replacement name for Thunberg's unavailable *fasciata*, thereby preserving the taxonomic concept while resolving the homonymy. Accordingly, *Rivetina baetica* (Rambur, 1838) was designated *nom. nov.* for Thunberg's *fasciata*, ensuring compliance with the Principle of Priority while maintaining nomenclatural stability. In this light, the species depicted by Savigny's Figure 14 is correctly referred to as *Rivetina baetica* (Rambur, 1838), and the temporary resurrection of *fasciata* in the early twentieth century must be regarded as an historically understandable but nomenclaturally invalid episode.

Taxonomic Designation. *Rivetina baetica* (Rambur, 1838)

Mantodea specimen male dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 15, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen male head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 15, aspect A) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 15 between 1827-2002.

- Burmeister, 1840: 27 *Miomantis fenestrata* (Fabricius, 1781)
 Saussure, 1870-71: 268 *Miomantis pellucida* Saussure, 1870
 Saussure, 1872: 69 *Miomantis savignyi*
 Westwood, 1889: 38 *Miomantis savignyi* Saussure, 1872
 Krauss, 1890: 237 *Miomantis savignyi* Saussure, 1872
 Werner, 1905: 53 *Miomantis savignyi* Saussure, 1872
 Innes, 1912: 71 *Miomantis savignyi* Saussure, 1872
 Storey, 1918: 57 *Miomantis savignyi* Saussure, 1872
 Ragge & Roy, 1967: 627 *Miomantis paykullii* Stal, 1871
 Ehrmann, 2002: 230 *Miomantis paykullii* Stal, 1871

Remarks. As with all of Savigny's material, the male *Miomantis* Saussure, 1870 specimen depicted in Figure 15 must have originated either from Egypt or from Israel, the regions traversed and documented during Napoleon's French expedition. Populations of *Miomantis* occurring in this northern sector of the sub-Saharan savanna belt typically exhibit an immaculate anterior surface of the forefemora, although, as emphasized by Ragge & Roy (1967: 627), "the systematics of the genus *Miomantis* has been largely based on the spots on the fore coxae and fore femora," characters that are demonstrably variable and therefore taxonomically unreliable when used in isolation. This variability underlies much of the historical instability surrounding the interpretation of Savigny's figure.

At the time of Burmeister's treatment (1840: 27), only two species of *Miomantis* were recognized: *fenestrata* from Sierra Leone and *monacha* Fabricius, 1787 from South Africa. Digital examination of the surviving type material of both taxa confirms that they possess rounded compound eyes. Savigny's Figure 15, however, clearly depicts a male with distinctly conical compound eyes from northern Africa. Burmeister nevertheless attributed this figure to his concept of *fenestrata*, having in his possession a pair of South African conical-eyed *Miomantis* that he believed to represent the Sierra Leone species. These South African specimens, now understood to belong to one of several conical-eyed taxa native to southern Africa and undescribed at the time, are neither conspecific with Fabricius's rounded-eyed *fenestrata* nor representative of the northern African population illustrated by Savigny. Ragge & Roy (1967: 627) explicitly confirmed that Burmeister's attribution of Savigny's Figure 15 to his "*fenestrata*" was erroneous, reflecting a conflation of geographically and morphologically distinct species.

Saussure described the valid species *pellucida* from Equatorial Africa and Senegal but mistakenly referred Savigny's Figure 15 to this taxon. Photographic examination of the male holotype of *pellucida* reveals an elongate, narrow pronotum, whereas Savigny's figure exhibits a comparatively shortened and more robust pronotum, clearly inconsistent with *pellucida*. Two years later, Saussure (1872: 69) described a Sudanese pair of *Miomantis* as a new species, *savignyi*, based upon a male with maculated forelegs and a female lacking such maculation, and correctly withdrew Savigny's Figure 15 from *pellucida*, reassigning it to *savignyi*. This attribution was widely accepted by subsequent authors (Westwood, Krauss, Werner, Innes, Storey). However, *savignyi* was unnecessary, as Stål (1871: 392) had already described the same species one year earlier as *paykullii*. Giglio-Tos (1927: 361) partially recognized the synonymy between the maculated and immaculate forms, and the matter was definitively resolved by Ragge & Roy (1967: 629), who synonymized *savignyi* with *paykullii*.

Photographic analysis of the male holotype of *paykullii* demonstrates a shortened, more robust pronotum in precise agreement with Savigny's Figure 15. Moreover, *paykullii* is a widespread species of the sub-Saharan savanna belt and occurs commonly in Egypt and Israel, precisely within the documented range of Savigny's collections, whereas *pellucida* does not occur in these regions. Accordingly, the specimen depicted in Figure 15 represents *Miomantis paykullii* Stål, 1871, and the subsequent proliferation of names—*fenestrata sensu* Burmeister, *pellucida sensu* Saussure, and *savignyi* Saussure—reflects a historical sequence of misattribution driven in part by overreliance on foreleg maculation and incomplete knowledge of African *Miomantis* diversity.

Taxonomic Designation. *Miomantis paykullii* Stal, 1871

Mantodea specimen male dorsal habitus (Plate 1, Figure 16, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen male head capsule (Plate 1, Figure 16, aspect A) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 1 Figure 16 between 1827-2002.

- Saussure, 1870-71: 251 *Ameles decolor* (Charpentier, 1825)
 Brunner, 1882: 68 *Ameles nana* (Charpentier, 1825)
 Westwood, 1889: 7 *Ameles decolor* (Charpentier, 1825)
 Krauss, 1890: 237 *Ameles nana* (Charpentier, 1825)
 Storey, 1918: 57 *Ameles nana* (Charpentier, 1825)
 Giglio-Tos, 1927: 162 *Ameles aegyptiaca* Werner, 1913
 Ehrmann, 2002: 58 *Ameles aegyptiaca* Werner, 1913

Remarks. The totality of historical, geographic, and morphological evidence supports the conclusion that Savigny’s Figure 16 represents *Ameles heldreichi*. The literature history demonstrates long-standing confusion surrounding this figure, with early authors variously assigning it to *decolor* or *nana*; however, both taxa are now known not to occur in the Levantine region, a point already recognized by Krauss in the nineteenth century who wrote that Savigny’s figure is “distinguished by the conically pointed eyes, such as otherwise occur only in *Ameles nana*, which, however, has not been found east of Sicily since Savigny.” Simon et al.’s 2025 synthesis of the Israeli Mantodea clarifies that only two *Ameles* Burmeister, 1838 species occur within Israel, *kervillei* and *heldreichi*, with *aegyptiaca* occurring in adjacent Egypt. Given that Savigny’s material derives from Napoleon’s Egyptian–Levantine campaigns, during which the French army traversed and briefly occupied both Egypt and the Levant, the geographic provenance of Savigny’s specimens must be restricted to these regions and cannot plausibly involve western Mediterranean taxa such as *decolor* or *nana*. Morphology further narrows the identification: Simon et al. (2025: 229) demonstrated that *kervillei* and *aegyptiaca* share a rounded dorsal surface of the compound eyes, a condition explicitly documented for *aegyptiaca* males and treated at length in their discussion of the *kervillei* complex. In contrast, the conically pointed dorsal surface of the compound eyes that is clearly illustrated in Savigny’s Figure 16 is diagnostic of *heldreichi* and absent in both *kervillei* and *aegyptiaca*. When the erroneous early assignments of *decolor* and *nana* are excluded on biogeographic grounds, and the compound eye morphology depicted by Savigny is evaluated against Simon et al.’s modern framework for Levantine *Ameles*, *heldreichi* emerges as the only species that both matches the distinctive conical-eyed condition and occurs within the historically and geographically constrained region of Savigny’s material.

Taxonomic Designation. *Ameles heldreichi* Brunner, 1882

Mantodea specimen female dorsal habitus (Plate 2, Figure 1, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female ventral habitus (Plate 2, Figure 1, aspect 2) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female foreleg (Plate 2, Figure 1, aspects b & b~) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female metathoracic tarsi (Plate 2, Figure 1, aspect d) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female mouthparts (Plate 2, Figure 1, aspects a, i, o & u) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen female antenna (Plate 2, Figure 1, aspect j) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 2 Figure 1 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
Lefebvre, 1835: 497 *Eremiaphila hralil* ?
Saussure, 1870-71: 386 *Eremiaphila nilotica*
Westwood, 1889: 2 *Eremiaphila nilotica* Saussure, 1871
Krauss, 1890: 238 *Eremiaphila nilotica* Saussure, 1871
Kirby, 1904: 212 *Eremiaphila nilotica* Saussure, 1871
Werner, 1905: 35 *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835
Innes, 1912: 61 *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835
Storey, 1918: 51 *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835
Giglio-Tos, 1927: 58 *Eremiaphila nilotica* Saussure, 1871
Ehrmann, 2002: 141 *Eremiaphila nilotica* Saussure, 1871

Remarks. Lefebvre (1835: 496) established *khamsin* on the basis of two female specimens originating from Suez and “Lower Egypt” respectively. Of these, the Lower Egyptian syntype is extant in the Paris museum (MNHN) and remains available for study, whereas the Suez syntype is evidently lost but survives unambiguously through Lefebvre’s own illustration (Plate XIII, fig. 3). Within the same publication, Lefebvre (1835: 497) described *hralil* from a single male that was also collected in “Lower Egypt”. This holotype is now evidently lost. In his original description of *khamsin*, Lefebvre noted that this species is “very compact and squat in its proportions, like *E. hralil*, with which it has a strong similarity in overall form.” He went further by openly questioning whether *khamsin* might represent nothing more than the female sex of *hralil*. Indeed, Lefebvre characterized *hralil* as gray-white, stocky, and 15 mm in length—characteristics that exactly match those he provided for *khamsin*. A photographic analysis of the surviving syntype of *khamsin* and review of Lefebvre’s other syntype that was figured in his work reveal that both are in close and concordant agreement with the female specimen depicted by Savigny’s Figure 1. Lefebvre also linked *hralil* to Savigny’s Figure 1, stating that his lone male appeared to correspond to the insect illustrated above and below as figures 1 and 2, i.e., the dorsal and ventral aspects of Savigny’s specimen. Lefebvre wrote that *hralil* was “found in the Desert of Minieh, in Lower Egypt”. This type location refers to the eastern desert margin adjacent to the modern city of Minya (El-Minya) along the east bank of the Nile Valley. During Napoleon’s French Campaign in Egypt and Ottoman Syria, military and scientific activity extended to the latitude of modern Minya, placing Savigny’s collecting efforts well within the same biogeographic corridor cited by Lefebvre for both *hralil* and *khamsin*. While Minya was not a long-term garrison center like Cairo, it lay directly along the occupied Nile corridor, and French presence there was real and documented. Even under a hypothetical argument minimizing Minya’s role as a permanent garrison, Napoleon’s forces indisputably occupied multiple regions that are biogeographically indistinguishable from the Minya desert margin, rendering any geographic separation between Savigny’s material and Lefebvre’s types untenable.

Taken together, the available evidence demonstrates that *khamsin* and *hralil* are not merely similar, but represent the female and male of a single species, with Savigny’s Figure 1 serving as the critical nexus anchoring this synonymy. The genus *Eremiaphila* Lefebvre, 1835 is characterized by brachypterous individuals, yet degrees of wing reduction vary among species. Although Lefebvre’s original description of *khamsin* did not explicitly mention the wings, his illustration of that taxon clearly depicts a micropterous female, a condition that is confirmed by direct photographic examination of the surviving syntype. Savigny’s Figure 1 likewise depicts a micropterous female, a condition that is both uncommon and taxonomically informative within *Eremiaphila*, and one that immediately distinguishes this taxon from sympatric congeners. Further, Lefebvre’s original description of *hralil* explicitly noted the presence of “rudiments of the elytra,” establishing that the male of *hralil* is also micropterous. This concordance in wing reduction between sexes provides a meaningful morphological linkage between *khamsin* and *hralil*, and in turn matches the female depicted by Savigny in Figure 1. As discussed, both taxa further share provenance in “Lower Egypt,” eliminating geographic separation between the material examined by

Savigny and that described by Lefebvre. Although Lefebvre stopped short of formally uniting the two names or designating Savigny's figure as the representative illustration of the same species, the evidentiary framework for doing so was already present in his work. When the shared micropterous condition of both sexes, identical body size and habitus, shared provenance, explicit statements of conspecificity, and direct reference to Savigny's illustration are considered together, they form a single, coherent synonymy nexus centered on Savigny's Figure 1. Accordingly, *khamsin* and *hralil* must be regarded as synonyms, with *khamsin* retained as the valid name due to the survival of name-bearing type material. Savigny's Plate 2, Figure 1 series is here interpreted as depicting the adult female of *Eremiophila khamsin*, and functions as the unifying morphological and historical anchor linking the female described as *khamsin* and the male described as *hralil* into a single species.

Saussure (1870–1871: 386) introduced *nilotica* based exclusively on Savigny's Figure 1, explicitly stating that the species was known only from Savigny's illustrations and that no physical specimens were available. He acknowledged the close resemblance of Savigny's figure to *khamsin* but proposed *nilotica* solely on the assertion that the illustrated individual appeared "twice as large" as *khamsin*. This rationale is fundamentally unsound, as Savigny's figure is a monochrome line engraving devoid of any scale bar, measurements, or descriptive text, rendering both size and coloration indeterminable. Nevertheless, Saussure paradoxically supplied precise coloration and a body length measurement for *nilotica*, data that cannot possibly be extracted from Savigny's illustration alone. His claim that *nilotica* was twice the size of *khamsin* is therefore entirely speculative and unsupported by the primary source upon which he explicitly based the name. Werner (1905: 35) recognized this flaw, observing that *khamsin* exhibits substantial size variation and that he possessed specimens approaching the size attributed by Saussure to *nilotica*, leading him to reject *nilotica* as a valid species altogether. Storey (1918: 51) articulated the logical synthesis of these observations, correctly recognizing that Savigny's Figure 1 represents the common and widespread *khamsin*, and that both *nilotica* and *hralil* are junior synonyms of that species. However, despite the absence of any published rebuttal or counter-argument, Storey's synonymy was subsequently ignored rather than evaluated. Later authors quietly reverted to Saussure's *nilotica* without explanation, justification, or reference to Storey's analysis. Through this process of unexamined reversion and repetition, *nilotica* acquired a false appearance of validity over time, not through evidentiary support but through citation inertia. This pattern exemplifies taxonomic drift, wherein a resolved taxonomic conclusion is progressively erased from practical usage without formal rejection, allowing an earlier, weaker interpretation to re-establish itself by default. As a result, *nilotica* has been treated as valid for over a century despite having been explicitly synonymized and never defensibly revalidated.

The subsequent addition of the suffix "-i" to *Eremiophila hralil* reflects a historical tendency to regularize species-group names under an assumed patronymic framework, but this practice is not nomenclaturally justified under the ICZN. The Code clearly distinguishes between permissible forms of species-group names and those circumstances under which an original spelling may be corrected. Under Article 31.2.1, a species-group epithet may be a noun in apposition, in which case it is indeclinable and must not be altered. Lefebvre's epithet *hralil* is fully Code-compliant as originally published and is best interpreted as a noun in apposition; there is no evidence that it refers to a person, nor did Lefebvre provide any indication of commemorative intent. Accordingly, any patronymic interpretation is speculative and unsupported. Mandatory correction under Article 32.5 applies only to demonstrable inadvertent errors, such as clear misspellings or typographical mistakes, and not to later authors' stylistic or grammatical preferences regarding Latinization. The alteration of *hralil* to *hralili* therefore does not constitute a correction but an intentional change to a correct original spelling, and as such represents an unjustified emendation under Article 33.2. The emended form does not displace the original name and must be treated as a junior objective synonym. Consequently, *Eremiophila hralil* Lefebvre, 1835 is the correct spelling, and the later genitive form has no standing under the Code.

Taxonomic Designation. *Eremiophila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835 = *Eremiophila hralil* Lefebvre, 1835 **stat. rev.** = *Eremiophila nilotica* Saussure, 1871 **stat. rev.** Because the synonymy of *hralil* and *nilotica* with

khamzin was explicitly established by Storey but subsequently ignored without rebuttal, the present action constitutes a restoration of status rather than a new synonymy.

Mantodea specimen dorsal habitus (Plate 2, Figure 2, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen head capsule (Plate 2, Figure 2, aspect A) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte, Histoire Naturelle*, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 2 Figure 2 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
 Lefebvre, 1835: 501 *Eremiaphila anubis*
 Saussure, 1870-71: 384 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
 Krauss, 1890: 238 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
 Kirby, 1904: 212 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
 Werner, 1905: 36 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
 Innes, 1912: 60 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
 Storey, 1918: 51 *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835
 Giglio-Tos, 1927: 60 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
 Ehrmann, 2002: 138 *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835

Remarks. Lefebvre's establishment of *anubis* was not based on recognition of a distinct species, but rather on a misinterpretation of Savigny's Figure 2, particularly with respect to wing structure and the taxonomic weight assigned to head capsule maculation. Lefebvre stated unequivocally that the insect depicted in Figure 2 was "beyond doubt in the nymphal state," and explicitly noted that he was unable to unite it with *khamsin* "because of the characters shown in the drawings of the posterior part of the head." This reliance on head capsule maculation, a highly variable and taxonomically unreliable character in *Eremiaphila*, constituted a primary barrier preventing him from associating Savigny's Figure 2 with either *khamsin* or evidently his own male specimen of *hralil*. Subsequent authors repeatedly questioned Lefebvre's interpretation of the depicted wings within Savigny's illustration as being representative of a nymph versus an adult. Saussure (1870–1871: 384) observed that, "judging from the figure, it indeed appears that even the wings constitute articulated organs". Werner (1905: 36) noted that "the apparently free wing margin is nothing more than the often very distinct suture between the wing and the metanotum." Modern understanding of *Eremiaphila* morphology resolves this ambiguity: nymphs of micropterous species exhibit continuous, uniformly textured meso/metanotal plates without clear demarcation of wing pads, whereas adults of micropterous species show a clearly articulated boundary between the thorax and freely separated wings, often with contrasting surface texture. The condition illustrated by Savigny in Figure 2 is therefore incompatible with a nymphal stage and instead indicates an adult micropterous specimen. Once Figure 2 is correctly interpreted as adult, Lefebvre's separation of

anubis rests solely on head capsule maculation, a character now recognized as insufficient for species delimitation. Storey (1918: 51) correctly synthesized these observations, concluding that “it is only reasonable to regard the insect figured as belonging, like Figures 1 and 2, to the variable species *E. khamsin*, and to sink the name *E. anubis* as a synonym, or variety, of *E. khamsin*.” However, despite the absence of any published rebuttal or counterargument, Storey’s synonymy was subsequently disregarded rather than evaluated. Later authors continued to list *anubis* uncritically, thereby perpetuating a name founded entirely on an illustration and on an erroneous assessment of developmental stage. Through repeated citation without reassessment, this unsupported name acquired a false appearance of taxonomic legitimacy. This pattern exemplifies another occurrence of taxonomic drift, whereby a resolved taxonomic judgment is gradually erased from practical usage not through refutation, but through neglect and silent reversion, allowing an objectively weaker interpretation to persist by default. In light of the articulated wing condition depicted by Savigny, the demonstrated variability of head maculation in *Eremiaphila*, and the historical recognition by Storey that the figure represents the widespread *khamsin*, *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835 is to be regarded as a junior synonym of *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835.

Taxonomic Designation. *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835 = *Eremiaphila anubis* Lefebvre, 1835
stat. rev. Because the synonymy of *anubis* with *khamsin* was explicitly established by Storey but subsequently ignored without rebuttal, the present action constitutes a restoration of status rather than a new synonymy.

Mantodea specimen dorsal habitus (Plate 2, Figure 3, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen foreleg (Plate 2, Figure 3, aspect b) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 2 Figure 3 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
 Lefebvre, 1835: 494 *Eremiaphila savigny*
 Saussure, 1870-71: 383 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835
 Krauss, 1890: 239 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835
 Kirby, 1904: 212 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835
 Werner, 1904: 405 *Centromantis savignyi* (Lefebvre, 1835)
 Werner, 1905: 46 *Centromantis savignyi* (Lefebvre, 1835)
 Innes, 1912: 56 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835
 Storey, 1918: 57 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835
 Giglio-Tos, 1927: 57 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835
 Ehrmann, 2002: 142 *Eremiaphila savignyi* Lefebvre, 1835

Remarks. Lefebvre (1835: 494) described *savigny* from a single adult female specimen that was sourced from Audinet-Serville's (formerly Latreille's) collection, having been labeled as originating from Egypt. Lefebvre matched his female holotype to Savigny's Figure 3, indicating that this illustration also represented a female of his newly described species. Werner (1905: 46) correctly noted that Figure 3 actually represents a conspecific male, pointing out that "the *Eremiaphila* figured by Savigny as Fig. 3 must be a male, judging from the armature of the anterior femora. Nevertheless, it is referred to as a female by Lefebvre, Saussure, and Krauss. I have, however, received a female of this very easily recognizable species... and I find that it lacks the elongated femoral spines". Aside from the initial confusion of the sex of the depicted specimen in Figure 3, the species assignment to this figure has remained stable for the past two centuries. However, the generic assignment of this species has experienced some turmoil.

In 1904, Werner established the genus *Centromantis* as distinct from *Eremiaphila*, diagnosing this new genus on the basis of the male forefemora being armed with greatly enlarged ultimate anteroventral spines and having sinuate foretibiae with a slight thickening near the tarsal insertion. On this basis, Werner transferred several species previously described under *Eremiaphila* into his new genus. Subsequent examination of these taxa, however, reveals that Werner's diagnosis conflated a valid, consistent character with an additional feature that is not uniformly expressed. In particular, the condition of sinuate foretibiae

in the male does not occur across all species that were included in *Centromantis*, rendering this aspect of the diagnosis untenable as a defining generic character. By contrast, the enlarged ultimate anteroventral spines of the male forefemora remain consistently present across all taxa historically associated with *Centromantis*. In species lacking this modification, the ultimate anteroventral spines are confluent with adjacent spines and do not differ markedly in size or shape. Among all material examined to date, no intermediate conditions have been observed, and the character appears binary in expression. The modification is currently known only from males; all examined females lack any corresponding differentiation. While sex-limited, this character is structurally discrete, developmentally coherent, and stable. Such sex-restricted traits are not uncommon at generic or subgeneric rank within Mantodea and are widely accepted when they are consistent and diagnostically robust. Despite this, *Centromantis* was synonymized with *Eremiaphila* by Giglio-Tos (1921: 6) without explanation or supporting analysis. No rationale was provided, no reassessment of Werner's diagnostic characters was undertaken, and no evidence of transitional conditions or morphological continuity was cited. Under modern taxonomic standards, this action is regarded as an unsupported subjective synonymy rather than a conclusion grounded in comparative character evaluation. The subsequent neglect of *Centromantis* appears to reflect historical inertia rather than the resolution of the underlying morphological question.

The core issue, therefore, is whether the discrete, apparently stable, sex-limited modification of the male anteroventral forefemoral spines represents an autapomorphy within a morphologically heterogeneous *Eremiaphila*, or whether it instead signals a lineage warranting formal taxonomic recognition. This reduces to a practical consideration of diagnosability. *Eremiaphila* as currently construed is already a broad and morphologically variable assemblage of desert-adapted mantises, united largely by general habitus and ecology rather than by clear synapomorphies. Absorbing a binary, non-overlapping male character of this nature without taxonomic recognition would further erode the explanatory and diagnostic coherence of the genus. Resolution of this question ultimately requires phylogenetic testing. A stepwise approach is warranted, beginning with sequencing of mitochondrial and/or nuclear markers across a representative sample of "*Centromantis*-like" taxa and typical *Eremiaphila*. Even modest molecular sampling, combined with a morphological character matrix, would allow cladistic or model-based analyses to test whether species bearing the enlarged ultimate anteroventral spines form a monophyletic group and to assess their placement relative to other *Eremiaphila*. Should these taxa form a well-supported clade, particularly if ecologically or geographically coherent, resurrection of *Centromantis* at generic rank would be justified, with appropriate new combinations. If monophyly is supported but the clade is deeply nested within *Eremiaphila*, subgeneric recognition would provide a compromise between phylogenetic signal and nomenclatural stability. Conversely, if the character proves homoplastic or weakly supported phylogenetically, continued synonymy would be appropriate, with the modification retained as a useful diagnostic feature in male identification keys.

Until such analyses are undertaken, the most defensible course is to revalidate *Centromantis* as a subgenus of *Eremiaphila*. Werner's original concept was partially flawed but not arbitrary: while tibial sinuosity alone cannot be sustained as a defining character, the modified ultimate anteroventral spines remain consistent, discrete, binary in expression, and strictly male-limited. Importantly, although the sinuate condition of the prothoracic tibiae has proven to be fluid and variably expressed, the species historically assigned to *Centromantis* share a broader and more coherent suite of characters that Werner did not explicitly articulate. These taxa are uniformly more elongate and gracile in overall habitus, with proportionally longer legs and a lighter, more gangly build that is plausibly associated with increased cursorial capacity. This contrasts sharply with the squat, heavier-bodied, and relatively shorter-legged morphology characteristic of typical *Eremiaphila*. Had this consistent habitus-level distinction been incorporated into Werner's original diagnosis, in conjunction with the modified ultimate anteroventral spines in the males, the concept of *Centromantis* would have rested on an even more stable morphological foundation. Reinstating *Centromantis* at subgeneric rank acknowledges the morphological signal expressed not only in discrete male armature but also in correlated aspects of overall body plan, without

overextending claims of phylogenetic certainty. Accordingly, *Centromantis* should be treated as a morphologically defined subgenus of *Eremiaphila*, diagnosed by the presence of enlarged, discrete ultimate anteroventral spines on the male forefemora, in conjunction with a consistently elongate, long-legged, lightly built habitus. This approach preserves diagnosability, corrects historical overreach, and establishes a clear framework for future phylogenetic testing. Given the binary nature of the primary character, the absence of intermediates, its consistency across multiple species, the congruence of associated habitus traits, and the weakness of the historical synonymy, such a revalidation is methodologically sound and preferable to continued uncritical synonymy.

The subsequent alteration of *Eremiaphila savigny* Lefebvre, 1835 to *savignyi* reflects the same later Latinizing practice discussed above for *khamsin* and *hralil*, namely the retrospective imposition of a genitive ending onto an original species-group name that was already Code-compliant as published. Although *savigny* is clearly derived from the surname of Savigny, the ICZN does not require that a species-group name based on a personal name be formed as a genitive, nor does it permit retroactive enforcement of patronymic intent where none was explicitly stated by the original author. As outlined earlier, species-group names published as nouns in apposition are indeclinable and must be retained in their original spelling unless demonstrably incorrect. Lefebvre provided no indication that *savigny* was intended as a Latin genitive, and there is no evidence of inadvertent error in the original spelling. Accordingly, the change to *savignyi* constitutes an unjustified emendation under Article 33.2 and does not displace the original name. The correct spelling is therefore *Eremiaphila savigny* Lefebvre, 1835.

Taxonomic Designation. *Eremiaphila* (*Centromantis* Werner, 1904, **stat. rev.**) *savigny* Lefebvre, 1835

Mantodea specimen dorsal habitus (Plate 2, Figure 4, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen foreleg (Plate 2, Figure 4, aspect b) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 2 Figure 4 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
 Lefebvre, 1835: 501 *Eremiaphila hebraica*
 Saussure, 1870-71: 382 *Eremiaphila hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835
 Krauss, 1890: 239 *Eremiaphila hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835
 Kirby, 1904: 211 *Eremiaphila hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835
 Werner, 1904: 405 *Centromantis hebraica* (Lefebvre, 1835)
 Werner, 1905: 46 *Centromantis hebraica* (Lefebvre, 1835)
 Storey, 1918: 57 *Eremiaphila hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835
 Giglio-Tos, 1927: 55 *Eremiaphila hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835
 Ehrmann, 2002: 139 *Eremiaphila hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835

Remarks. Savigny's Figure 4 has enjoyed unusual nomenclatural stability relative to other figures in the *Description de l'Égypte*, and its identity as *hebraica* has remained essentially unchallenged since its introduction. Lefebvre's original treatment was concise, noting the presence of shortened wings as evidence that the illustrated specimen represented a brachypterous adult. Lefebvre explicitly based the name *hebraica* solely on Savigny's illustration, and no physical type material has ever existed; consequently, Savigny's Figure 4 must be regarded as the iconotype of the species. Werner (1905: 46) correctly recognized that the distinct enlargement of the two ultimate anteroventral femoral spines that are depicted in aspect b of Figure 4 unambiguously places this taxon within *Centromantis*. Although Werner acknowledged that he had not examined specimens personally, he nevertheless concluded that the illustration alone was sufficient to establish generic placement. He further observed that, despite the absence of subsequent records after Savigny, the species "certainly belongs to this purely African genus" and should be assigned with confidence to the Egyptian fauna even in the absence of explicit locality data. This geographic inference is corroborated by modern faunal treatments, including the exclusion of *hebraica* from the Israeli mantodean fauna (Simon et al., 2025), which strongly suggests that Savigny's specimen originated in Egypt rather than in the Levantine portion of Napoleon's campaign; had the species been present in Israel, it would almost certainly have been detected and documented there. The retention of *hebraica* in *Eremiaphila* by Storey, even prior to Giglio-Tos's unsupported synonymization of

Centromantis with *Eremiaphila* in 1921, appears best explained as another instance of taxonomic drift rather than reasoned disagreement, as Storey offered no conceptual argument against the validity of *Centromantis* or the placement of *hebraica* within it. Taken together, the stability of usage, the clarity of the diagnostic characters visible in Savigny's illustration, and Werner's cogent morphological interpretation support the continued recognition of *hebraica* as a distinct taxon, with Savigny's Figure 4 serving as its definitive name-bearing representation.

Taxonomic Designation. *Eremiaphila* (*Centromantis* Werner, 1904, **stat. rev.**) *hebraica* Lefebvre, 1835

Mantodea specimen dorsal habitus (Plate 2, Figure 5, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen foreleg (Plate 2, Figure 5, aspects b~ & b) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

Mantodea specimen metathoracic tarsi (Plate 2, Figure 5, aspect d) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 2 Figure 5 between 1827-2002.

Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.

Lefebvre, 1835: 503 *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* nymph

Audinet-Serville, 1838: 214 *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835 nymph

Saussure, 1870-71: 367 *Heteronychotarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835 nymph

Krauss, 1890: 240 *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835

Kirby, 1904: 212 *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835 nymph (?)
Werner, 1905: 52 *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835
Innes, 1912: 42 *Heteronytarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835
Storey, 1918: 57 *Heteronytarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835
Giglio-Tos, 1927: 61 *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835

Remarks. The taxonomic assignment of Figure 5 has remained notably stable for nearly two centuries, with all subsequent interpretations consistently associating the illustrated specimen with *aegyptiacus*, apart from recurrent orthographic errors in the generic name. Lefebvre (1835: 501) established *Heteronutarsus* as a genus distinct from *Eremiaphila* on the basis of tarsal morphology, explicitly rejecting the possibility that the observed condition represented a developmental anomaly. He emphasized the consistent reduction in tarsomere number as a stable and diagnostic generic character: the foretibial tarsi bear four tarsomeres, the meso/metathoracic tibial tarsi bear only three, and the apical tibial claws of the meso/metathoracic legs are markedly unequal in length. These characters, taken together, clearly separate *Heteronutarsus* from *Eremiaphila*, in which a higher tarsomere count and more symmetrical claws are the norm. Lefebvre described the type species *aegyptiacus* from a single adult female holotype and explicitly linked this specimen to the nymph illustrated in Figure 5, correctly interpreting the figure as representing the immature stage of the same taxon. Subsequent authors uniformly accepted this interpretation. Saussure inadvertently introduced the spelling *Heteronytarsus* without comment, a change best interpreted as a *lapsus calami*, as he elsewhere spelled the genus correctly, explicitly discussed Lefebvre's diagnosis, and clearly intended to reference the original name. A different incorrect spelling was later adopted by Innes and Storey, following Brullé's (1835: 76) earlier introduction of this orthographic error, but without any accompanying taxonomic or conceptual revision. These variant genus spellings do not reflect disagreement over the identity or placement of Savigny's Figure 5, which has consistently been understood as representing the nymphal stage of *aegyptiacus*. Accordingly, Savigny's illustration stands as an early and accurate depiction of this taxon with long-standing stability.

Taxonomic Designation. *Heteronutarsus aegyptiacus* Lefebvre, 1835

Mantodea specimen dorsal habitus (Plate 2, Figure 6, aspect 1) from Savigny in *Description de l'Égypte*, Histoire Naturelle, Panckoucke edition (1827)

References to the species depicted on Plate 2 Figure 6 between 1827-2002.

- Audouin, 1827: 440 *Mantis* sp.
 Lefebvre, 1835: 489 *Eremiaphila zetterstedt* ?
 Audinet-Serville, 1838: 212 *Eremiaphila zetterstedtii* Lefebvre, 1835 ?
 Saussure, 1870-71: 383 *Eremiaphila brevipennis*
 Westwood, 1889: 2 *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871
 Krauss, 1890: 240 *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871
 Kirby, 1904: 212 *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871
 Werner, 1905: 42 *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871
 Storey, 1918: 51 *Eremiaphila khamsin* Lefebvre, 1835
 Giglio-Tos, 1927: 58 *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871
 Ehrmann, 2002: 138 *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871 (nymph)

Remarks. Lefebvre established *zetterstedt* on the basis of two adult female specimens collected in the “Desert of Suez,” and only tentatively associated this taxon with Savigny’s Figure 6, which he implicitly regarded as representing a nymph. This assumption was influenced by Lefebvre’s interpretation of reduced wings as indicative of immaturity, as *zetterstedt* was described and illustrated as brachypterous while Savigny’s Figure 6 depicts an individual with either underdeveloped wing pads or a micropterous condition.

Illustration of *Eremiaphila zetterstedt* female syntype, Plate XII, figure 3 from Lefebvre’s *Nouveau groupe d'Orthoptères de la famille des Mantides* (1835)

A serious discrepancy exists between Lefebvre’s written description of *zetterstedt* and his own illustration of the taxon. Lefebvre described the pronotum as “almost square, as wide anteriorly as posteriorly, with sides little dilated and protuberances weakly marked,” implying a compact, weakly sculptured, near-quadrate structure. In contrast, the illustrated pronotum is distinctly trapezoidal, clearly broader anteriorly, with pronounced lateral expansion and conspicuous dorsal relief. These two characterizations are not reconcilable through intraspecific variation or interpretive latitude and instead represent fundamentally different morphological states. This inconsistency is best interpreted as a disconnect between illustration and descriptive synthesis: Lefebvre’s figure emphasizes outline and relief for visual clarity, whereas the text reflects a reductive comparative abstraction that under-represents anterior expansion and sculpturing. Because the illustration is internally consistent and shows no indication of engraving distortion, it must be accorded primary evidentiary weight. Consequently, the pronotal morphology of *zetterstedt* should be interpreted as anteriorly broadened and sculptured as shown in Lefebvre’s illustration, with the textual description regarded as incomplete rather than corrective.

Lefebvre’s illustrated *zetterstedt* is morphologically incompatible with Savigny’s Figure 6. The pronotum in Figure 6 is distinctly rectangular rather than trapezoidal, lacks expanded prozonal angles, and shows only slight anterior widening; moreover, its maximum width is substantially narrower than the head capsule. Lefebvre explicitly described the head of *zetterstedt* as “large, as wide as the prothorax,” a relationship clearly depicted in his own illustration but absent from Savigny’s figure. In addition, Lefebvre described and illustrated the abdominal tergites of *zetterstedt* as rugose, whereas the tergites in Figure 6 are smooth. Even if Savigny’s specimen were to represent a nymph, these combined differences in pronotal architecture, head–pronotum proportions, and abdominal sculpture are too great to support

conspecificity. Lefebvre's expressed doubt in associating Figure 6 with *zetterstedt* is therefore well founded, and Figure 6 must represent a distinct species.

Saussure (1870–1871: 383) explicitly rejected Lefebvre's tentative association, stating that Lefebvre is “consistently mistaken with species possessing rudimentary elytra—which he takes for nymphs—refers this species, doubtfully it is true but without any justification, to *zetterstedtii*. The latter is much smaller and does not have so narrow a prothorax.” On this basis, Saussure treated the specimen illustrated in Figure 6 as a distinct taxon, naming it *brevipennis*, emphasizing its proportionally narrower pronotum. This interpretation was subsequently adopted by Westwood, Krauss, and Kirby. Werner (1905: 42) expressed some reservation, however, noting that *brevipennis* differed from *khamsin* “only in a few points,” yet he nevertheless retained *brevipennis* as distinct and did not propose synonymy. Storey (1918: 51) misrepresented Werner's position, incorrectly asserting that Werner had synonymized *brevipennis* with *khamsin* and extended this error to unite Savigny's Figures 1, 2, and 6 under a single species. Werner, however, made no such taxonomic act, and comparative examination of Figure 6 against the conspecific *khamsin* pair illustrated in Figures 1 and 2 demonstrates clear differences in head–pronotum proportions and pronotal architecture that are diagnostic of a separate taxon. Storey's interpretation was rejected by Giglio-Tos and Ehrmann, both of whom continued to recognize *brevipennis* as distinct and represented by Savigny's Figure 6.

Saussure listed the habitat of *brevipennis* as Egypt, a conclusion supported by modern biogeographic evidence. The recent treatment of the Israeli mantodean fauna by Simon et al. (2025), documenting five species of *Eremiaphila* from that region and excluding *brevipennis*, strongly indicates that Savigny's specimen originated in Egypt rather than the Levantine portion of Napoleon's campaign. Had the species occurred in Israel, it would almost certainly have been detected and recorded there. Accordingly, Savigny's Figure 6 represents *brevipennis*, a distinct Egyptian species, and not *zetterstedt* nor any form of *khamsin*.

Taxonomic Designation. *Eremiaphila brevipennis* Saussure, 1871

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